

Local Government in Poland

Responses to Urban-Rural Challenges

edited by

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The H2020-MSCA-RISE-2018 project aims to provide solutions for local governments that address the fundamental challenges resulting from urbanisation. To address these complex issues, 18 partners from 17 countries and six continents share their expertise and knowledge in the realms of public law, political science, and public administration. LoGov identifies, evaluates, compares, and shares innovative practices that cope with the impact of changing urban-rural relations in major local government areas (WP 1-5).

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People's Participation in Local Decision-Making

6.1. People's Participation in Local Decision-Making in Poland: An Introduction

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The process of local community empowerment which started in Poland after 1989 was an important element of political transformation. The priority was to return to guarantee the residents the right to participate in exercising the public authority and in deciding on own matters. The adopted model of local government is based on representative democracy. The Polish citizens and EU citizens residing in Poland from the age of 18 years are guaranteed the active voting right. Similarly, it applies to the passive voting right. The election for the mayor in the community is the exception: the passive voting right is only granted to Polish citizens from the age of 25 years old.

Since the beginning of local government an instrument of direct democracy – a local referendum was also introduced. The decisions are binding when certain requirements are met. The local referendum can be conducted at any level of local government, i.e. in the *gmina*, *powiat* and voivodeship. All own tasks of local government, except the matters explicitly excluded by law (a negative catalogue), are the subject of the referendum. A special referendum is the referendum on self-taxation of residents of the *gmina* for public purposes (this is an exception to the general rule that the taxes can be imposed on the citizens only by the Polish Parliament). Furthermore, the residents have the right to recall in the referendum these local government bodies which were elected by them by direct universal suffrage. According to the constitutional principle in Poland all representative bodies are elected by direct universal suffrage. Since 2002 the executive body in the *gmina* is also elected by direct universal suffrage. The executive bodies in the *powiat* and voivodeship are elected and recalled by the representative bodies.

A local referendum is held at the initiative of the representative body or at the request of inhabitants. The initiative to hold a referendum at the request of the local government unit residents may be applied by:

- the minimum 5 citizens (referendum in the *gmina*), minimum 15 citizens (referendum in the *powiat* and voivodeship);
- a political party local branch operating in a given local government unit (*gmina*, *powiat*, voivodeship);
- a social organization with legal personality and operating in a given local government unit (*gmina*, *powiat*, voivodeship).

The period of collecting signatures lasts 60 days. In order to hold a local referendum to be valid, it must be signed by:

- 10 per cent of the *gmina* or powiat residents eligible to vote;
- 5 per cent of voivodship residents eligible to vote.

The criterion for the validity of a referendum in Poland is a voter turnout. It was set at 30 per cent. The result of a referendum is conclusive if more than half of the valid votes were cast in favor of one of the solutions in a matter put to a referendum (on self-taxation of inhabitants for public purposes – the majority of 2/3 of valid votes).

The 30 per cent turnout threshold has been modified since 2005 in the case of a referendum on the dismissal of a directly¹⁷⁸ elected local authority. Currently, the minimum turnout is 3/5 of the participants in the election of the body¹⁷⁹ to be dismissed.

In general, approx. 10 per cent of referendums are successful, the main problem is reaching the required turnout. Average turnout is 17 per cent. Most frequently referendums are held in *gminas*, very rarely in *powiats*, and incidentally in voivodeships. In *gminas*, referendums on the dismissal of the mayor are held most often. The referenda on the recalling of the executive bodies in the large cities elicit the particular interest of the public (negative result: Warsaw 2013, Bytom 2017; positive result: Olsztyn 2008, Elbląg 2013).

Body	Three terms of office 2002-2014		Term of office 2014-2018	
	Number of referendums	Valid referendums	Number of referendums	Valid referendums
The <i>gmina</i> council	67	10	14	1
The mayor	246	32	44	4
The <i>powiat</i> council	8	0	0	0
The voivodeship assembly (council)	1	0	0	0

Table 1: Local referendums on the dismissal of bodies.¹⁸⁰

The table shows that since 2002 (when the direct election of the mayor was introduced) a total of 380 referendums have been held only 9 per cent of which were valid. Referendums on the dismissal of the mayor are most common and they account for 76 per cent of all referendums on the dismissal of local government bodies.

If we consider the structure of *gminas* in which referendums on the dismissal of the *gmina's* council and/or the mayor were held in the years 2014-2018, the majority of them were either rural *gminas* (26) or urban and rural *gminas* (12), small towns (6), large cities with *powiat* rights (2).

¹⁷⁸ In *gminas*, inhabitants directly elect both bodies (the *gmina* council and the mayor), in the *powiats* and in the voivodeships, only the representative body (the *powiat* council and the voivodeship assembly).

¹⁷⁹ Act of 15 September 2000 on Local Referendum.

¹⁸⁰ Own work based on 'Referenda odwoławcze w kadencji 2014 – 2018' (*Referendum lokalne*) <<http://referendumlokalne.pl/referenda-w-kadencji-2014-2018>> accessed 1 December 2019 and Paweł Cieśliński, 'Referendum lokalne w Polsce – ale jakie?' (2016) 3 *Civitas et Lex* 28, 33.

Substantive referendums are carried out much less frequently. The report of the Chancellery of the President of the Republic of Poland of 6 September 2013 on local referendums indicates that in the period 2010-2013 there were 111 referendums on the dismissal of local authorities and only 22 substantive referendums.¹⁸¹

In 2011, a provision was introduced to the Act on *Gmina* Self-Government on the possibility of holding a local referendum at the request of inhabitants on the change in the establishment, merger, division and liquidation of a *gmina* and the establishment of the *gmina's* borders.

The institution of 'citizens' resolution-making initiative' (*obywatelska inicjatywa uchwałodawcza*) was provided for in the rules on law making by the local government at all three levels of local government. The draft resolution presented by the residents becomes the subject of the agenda of the legislative body of local government unit at the next session after the presentation of the draft resolution, however, not later than after expiry of 3 months from the date of the presentation of the draft resolution.

Besides the direct exercise of local government authority (local government elections and local referenda) there is a series of opportunities for the residents to participate in the decision-making processes. The instruments of participation were institutionalized in Poland gradually. Since the beginning the acts on local government guaranteed the residents the right to be consulted – the consultation can be carried out in all matters important for the residents. The public consultation allows the members of local government community to participate in the conduct of public matters. The acts make it obligatory to conduct the consultation, inter alia, with regard to: (i) change to the boundaries, merger, division, liquidation of local government units, (ii) establishment of auxiliary units in municipalities (districts, civil parishes).

The consultation may also take the form of permanent consultation bodies. The Act of 8 March 1990 on *Gmina* Self-Government provides for two such bodies: youth council (since 2011) and council of seniors (since 2013).

Poland also belongs to the states which promote new forms of participation, such as a participatory budget. The first participatory budget came into operation in Sopot in 2011, then, fairly quickly, such initiatives were undertaken by larger or very large cities. Till 2018 the local government authorities based on the general provisions of local government acts on the consultation. In 2018 the acts on *Gmina* Self-Government, on *Powiat* Self-Government and on Voivodeship Self-Government were extended by the regulations on the 'citizens' budget' (*budżet obywatelski*) as a special form of the consultation. It is surprising that the act made it obligatory to establish a participatory budget in the cities with *powiat* rights. Therefore, it is a characteristic element of the system of large cities.

¹⁸¹ 'Referenda Lokalne' (Chancellery of the President of the Republic of Poland 2013) <https://www.prezydent.pl/gfx/prezydent/userfiles2/files/2013_pliki_rozne/raport_referenda/referenda_lokalne_raport_kprp_20130925_131447.pdf> accessed 10 December 2019.

In Poland there is also an instrument of budgetary participation dedicated only to the rural communes – ‘The Village fund’ (*fundusz sołecki*). Since its inception in 2009 it is anchored in the act, now, it is the Act of 2011 on the Village Fund.

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